

Mobile Apps on a Global Scale

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The variable "Number of Mobile Apps Created per Billion Dollars of GDP at Purchasing Power Parity (PPP)" represents a measure of mobile app development activity within a country in relation to its economy. This variable combines two fundamental concepts: mobile app production and the economic size of a country, expressed in terms of GDP adjusted for purchasing power parity. GDP at purchasing power parity (PPP) allows for the comparison of different countries' economies by taking into account differences in the cost of living and local price levels. This adjustment helps overcome the limitations of direct comparisons between nominal GDPs, which often do not accurately reflect the actual purchasing power of citizens in different countries. The variable expresses the number of mobile apps developed in a given country in relation to a billion dollars of PPP-adjusted GDP, providing a measure of the intensity with which a country generates technological innovations in the field of mobile applications relative to its economic strength. This metric is useful for comparing countries of different economic sizes. For example, a country with a high number of mobile apps created per billion dollars of PPP GDP could be considered particularly innovative or tech-oriented, while a country with a lower value might have a less developed tech ecosystem or focus on other economic sectors. The measure can be influenced by several factors, including the availability of qualified human resources, technological infrastructure, policies supporting innovation, and access to global digital markets. In summary, this variable provides an indication of a country's ability to develop mobile apps relative to its economy, considering differences in levels of prosperity and cost of living. The data refers to the period between 2018 and 2022.

Number of Mobile Apps Relative to GDP at Purchasing Power Parity on an International Level in 2022. The data on the number of mobile apps created per billion dollars of GDP at purchasing power parity (PPP) in 2022 reveals significant variability among countries, highlighting notable differences in technological innovation and the development of digital economies. Leading the ranking is Cyprus, with a remarkable value of 100 mobile apps created per billion dollars of PPP GDP, standing out significantly from other countries. This could reflect a particularly favorable technological ecosystem, supported by government policies that incentivize digital sector development and a dynamic community of developers. Countries like Belarus (52.8), Israel (47.8), Singapore (42), and Hong Kong (37.9) also show strong activity in mobile app development relative to their economic size, suggesting that these nations have successfully capitalized on local technological talent and advanced digital infrastructure. A group of Nordic and Eastern European countries, such as Estonia (36.1), Lithuania (35.6), Finland (28.9), and Sweden (26.3), confirms their reputation as hubs of technological innovation, though the number of apps per billion dollars of GDP is lower compared to the leading countries. However, the relatively high value for smaller economies demonstrates that these nations have succeeded in creating favorable environments for technological development, thanks to targeted investments in education, digital infrastructure, and startup-friendly policies. Among advanced economies, the positioning of the United States (16.2), the United Kingdom (15.1), Germany (8), and Japan (9.7) is surprising. Despite their dominant role in the global technology sector, they record lower values compared to some less economically developed nations. This could be attributed to the fact that, in large economies, app production is spread across a much larger GDP, diluting the relative number of apps per billion dollars of GDP. Additionally, it is possible that these

advanced economies are more focused on broader technological development sectors, beyond just mobile apps, such as artificial intelligence, robotics, or other areas of technological innovation. Countries like Vietnam (29.2) and Pakistan (20.2) stand out among emerging economies for their high number of apps created relative to their PPP GDP. This indicates a growing momentum in the mobile app sector, likely driven by a young population, increasing smartphone adoption, and rapid development of technological infrastructure. Vietnam, in particular, is emerging as a technological hub in Southeast Asia, benefiting from foreign investment and policies encouraging local innovation. On the other hand, countries like Italy (3.5), Belgium (2.1), and Spain (12.1) report relatively low numbers of mobile apps created compared to their economic size, suggesting a lower emphasis on this specific technological sector or a slower adoption of policies aimed at fostering digital innovation. At the lower end of the ranking, countries like Yemen, Myanmar, and Tajikistan show almost negligible values, reflecting a lack of digital infrastructure and qualified human capital to compete in the global tech sector. In summary, the data shows that there is no direct correlation between a country's economic level and its ability to develop mobile apps. Smaller and less wealthy countries, like Cyprus or Belarus, can have surprisingly vibrant digital ecosystems, while larger economies may appear less dynamic in the mobile app sector, possibly focusing on other technological areas. The ranking also highlights the importance of government policies, technological infrastructure, and local talent in determining a country's success in developing mobile apps.

Number of Mobile Apps Relative to GDP at Purchasing Power Parity on an International Level Between 2018 and 2022. The data on the number of mobile apps created per billion dollars of GDP at purchasing power parity (PPP) provides a varied picture of technological development and economic dynamics in different nations between 2018 and 2022. A general reading reveals divergent trends, with some countries experiencing a significant increase in mobile app creation, while others have seen a drastic reduction. A first group of countries, including Costa Rica, Kazakhstan, and Kenya, has seen a remarkable increase in the number of apps developed relative to GDP. Costa Rica, for example, recorded an impressive 425% increase, rising from 0.40 to 2.10 apps per billion dollars of GDP, signaling a growing technological ecosystem. Kazakhstan showed a similar rise of 150%, while Kenya saw an increase of 133%. These data indicate that some developing or emerging countries are leveraging digitalization to expand their technological sectors. On the contrary, many advanced and developed economies have experienced a decline in the number of apps created. The United States, for instance, saw a 61.24% reduction, with a significant drop from 41.80 to 16.20 apps. Countries like the United Kingdom (-55.59%) and Germany (-66.53%) show similar negative trends. This decrease could reflect a saturation of the mobile app market in more developed countries, where competition is higher, and the growth potential may be more limited compared to emerging economies. Furthermore, advanced economies might place more emphasis on larger, more complex technological projects, such as artificial intelligence and automation, which may not necessarily be reflected in the number of mobile apps created. An interesting case is represented by countries like Singapore and Cyprus, where values remained stable. Singapore registered only a modest increase of 7.69%, while Cyprus maintained the same number of apps created in both years (100). This could indicate that in some economies, once a certain level of technological maturity is reached, the creation of new apps stabilizes or grows at a slower pace. However, the most drastic declines are observed in countries like the Republic of Korea (-62.58%), Switzerland (-64.76%), and Canada (-66.16%). These figures may indicate reduced competitiveness in the mobile app market or a shift in focus toward other technological sectors. In general, the data reflects two main dynamics. First, in developing countries and emerging economies, there is significant growth in mobile app creation, driven by

increased technological accessibility and the potential to tap into new digital markets. Second, developed economies, which have historically been leaders in producing innovative technologies, are now experiencing stagnation or decline in the number of apps created, likely due to market saturation and a shift in focus to advanced technologies beyond mobile apps. Lastly, some countries, particularly those in crisis or facing economic and political instability, such as Yemen (-95.65%) and South Africa (-92.61%), have seen a sharp drop in app creation, likely due to internal structural factors that limit technological innovation and the growth of the digital sector.

Conclusions. The value of the analyzed variable decreased on average from 21.37 to 11.36, representing a reduction of -10.02 units, equivalent to -46.86%. The top performers are: Costa Rica with +425.00%, Kazakhstan with +150.00%, Kenya with +133.33%, El Salvador with +100.00%, and Belarus with +78.98%. The worst performers are Qatar with -83.87%, Georgia with -87.83%, South Africa with -92.61%, Yemen with -96.65%, and the Kyrgyz Republic with -97.14%.

Performance	Countries	2018	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Top Performance	Costa Rica	0,40	2,10	1,70	425,00
	Kazakhstan	1,20	3,00	1,80	150,00
	Kenya	0,30	0,70	0,40	133,33

	El Salvador	0,10	0,20	0,10	100,00
	Belarus	29,50	52,80	23,30	78,98
Worse Performance	Qatar	3,10	0,50	-2,60	-83,87
	Georgia	18,90	2,30	-16,60	-87,83
	South Africa	17,60	1,30	-16,30	-92,61
	Yemen, Rep.	2,30	0,10	-2,20	-95,65
	Kyrgyz Republic	3,50	0,10	-3,40	-97,14

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